

Exploring Complementary Approaches: Traditional Chinese Medicine and Naturopathy in Interstitial Cystitis Management.

Cátia Lopes^{1*}.

¹ ABS – Health Level, Atlântico Business School, Vila Nova de Gaia, Porto, Portugal.

* Correspondence: catiasdl@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Interstitial cystitis (IC) is a chronic, progressive, and recurrent urological condition characterized by pelvic pain and urinary dysfunction. The disease significantly impairs patients' physical health and psychological well-being, presenting a challenge for conventional therapeutic approaches. **Objective:** This narrative review aims to explore the distinct contributions of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) and Naturopathy in the management of interstitial cystitis, highlighting their principles, treatment strategies, and potential benefits. **Methods:** A selection of relevant literature was conducted through searches in databases including PubMed, Scopus, and ScienceDirect, as well as specialized books and reference texts. **Results/Conclusion:** Despite the limited availability of high-quality clinical studies, the findings suggest that an integrative approach combining TCM and Naturopathy may offer promising complementary strategies for managing IC. Such approaches may contribute to safer, more personalized, and holistic care for affected individuals. Further robust and long-term studies are needed to confirm their effectiveness and cost-efficiency, particularly in light of the economic burden of IC.

Keywords: Interstitial Cystitis, Chronic Pelvic Pain, Traditional Chinese Medicine, Naturopathy.

Citation: Lopes C., Silva M.G., Silva R.P. Exploring Complementary Approaches: Traditional Chinese Medicine and Naturopathy in Interstitial Cystitis Management. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(2) 10.5281/zenodo.15545207

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 02 April 2025

Reviewed: 10 May 2025

Revised: 23 May 2025

Accepted: 27 May 2025

Published: 29 May 2025

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Interstitial cystitis (IC), also known as chronic pelvic pain (CPP) or bladder pain syndrome (BPS), is a long-lasting condition that mainly affects women^{1,2}. In this paper, the first nomenclature will be assumed.

According to the Society for Urodynamics and Female Urology (SUFU), IC is characterized by persistent pelvic pain and urinary irritative symptoms lasting for more than six weeks, in the absence of infection or other identifiable causes³. It can affect women's quality of life and interfere with their physical, mental, and social well-being⁴.

However, IC can affect more than the individual's health. It is not only a chronic condition, as previously mentioned, but also progressive and recurrent in nature⁵. This progression results in a "snowball effect", as the disease advances, the patient's health deteriorates, leading to an increase in treatment needs and a financial burden as a consequence⁵.

In order to understand the impact of IC in women's lives the data reveal that 15% of women had to miss time from work and report reduced productivity, resulting in a loss of income of \$4,216 per year^{6,7}.

Regarding direct costs of IC (including consultations, medication, hospitalizations, and other interventions), these are higher than those associated with diseases such as diabetes, depression, hypertension, or asthma. Also, it is estimated that a woman with IC has approximately 2.5 times the expenses when compared to a male with the same condition^{6,7}.

A study involving 239 women diagnosed with IC and receiving treatment estimated an annual cost of \$6,614. Another study, based on 43 women with IC, reported an average annual cost of \$3,631 per person according to the Medicare database. It is further estimated that, without insurance, this amount could triple ⁸.

Although the aetiology of the disease is still a matter of debate, it is known that factors such as dysfunction of the bladder epithelium, microvascular changes, autoimmunity, infection either by ketamine or metabolites and imbalances in the central nervous system may be involved ^{3,9}. Due to the multifactorial nature of IC and the difficulty of diagnosis, conventional treatment does not always offer definitive solutions, leading many patients to seek complementary therapies ¹⁰.

While TCM presents a holistic approach that aims to treat the underlying causes of disease by balancing the flow of energy (*Qi*) and restoring harmony between the body's systems ¹¹, Naturopathy emphasizes the body's intrinsic capacity for self-healing, disease prevention, and individual responsibility in achieving health ¹².

This narrative review explores the Traditional Chinese Medicine and Naturopathic views on the treatment of interstitial cystitis, looking at practices such as acupuncture, herbal medicine, Tai Chi, *Qigong* and dietary change, as well as the scientific evidence that supports them.

2. Interstitial Cystitis Pathogenesis and Aetiology

IC is more common in women aged 30-50 years with the prevalence is about 2.70% in women and almost 10 times less frequent in men. However, every year these numbers tend to rise ^{13,14}.

Studies have indicated that IC affects 400,000 individuals in the UK (United Kingdom) and between 3 to 8 million women and 1 to 4 million men in the USA (United States of America) ^{15,16}.

As previously mentioned, IC can be very frustrating for both patient and physician because it can be very difficult to find the causes affecting the individual. These causes can be structural, functional or even both ¹⁷.

Although no definitive pathogenic agent or mechanism has been identified as the cause of interstitial cystitis, there are some hypotheses already studied ^{4,18,19}. The first one, and the most common, claims that a deregulation of the bladder urothelium leads to a migration of urinary solutes across the urothelial barrier leading to symptoms ^{4,18-20}. This leakage may result from alterations in glycosaminoglycans, proteoglycans, cell adhesion proteins and some defense molecules which makes the bladder epithelium reactive to harmless substances and additionally causing pain ^{4,18-20}.

Another hypothesis is the "cross-organ" theory, which proposes that the function (or dysfunction) of one organ can physiologically affect another. For example, irritable bowel syndrome can directly influence the sensory properties of bladder C-fibers ^{4,20}.

Ultimately, autoimmune mechanisms, mast cell activation, previous diseases and infections, neuropathic changes and some environmental factors also play a role in the pathogenesis ^{14,19}. In these cases, we cannot say that we can achieve a cure (not having pain again). It is imperative to manage patient expectations ²¹.

2.1. Interstitial Cystitis – TCM diagnosis hypotheses

According to the "Guiding Principles for Clinical Research of New Chinese Medicine", cystitis corresponds to a damp-heat-stasis syndrome ¹³ or damp-cold stasis syndrome if it is nonbacterial cystitis ²².

Although both syndromes are related to IC, they present different diagnostic criteria (Table 1). Damp-cold stasis syndrome is more closely associated with IC.

Table 1. Characteristics and criteria of damp heat and cold syndrome ²².

Syndrome Characteristics	Damp-heat-stasis syndrome	Damp-cold stasis syndrome
Urine	Dark and cloudy, sometimes with hematuria	Frequent urge to urinate, with difficulty in micturition and a sensation of heaviness in the lower abdomen
Tongue	May appear red, thick, with a yellow and sticky coating	May have a white, sticky coating at the root of the tongue
Pulse	Rapid and slippery	Slippery
Causes	Emotional burden, weakened immune system, or exposure to external damp-heat or damp-cold	Kidney <i>Qi</i> deficiency or excessive fear

The International Classification of Diseases (ICD), developed by the World Health Organization (WHO), is a widely used system for diagnosing, monitoring, and classifying diseases on a global level, including TCM ²³. The ICD-11 enhances diagnostic precision by integrating current scientific knowledge, adapting to epidemiological trends, and refining coding for chronic, rare, and mental health conditions ²³. Therefore, according to Chapter 26 of ICD-11, titled Traditional Medicine, i.e., the chapter of ICD-11 that allows for the establishment of the diagnosis according to ancient Chinese medicine, we believe that IC may be encoded with SA90, SA58, and SB07, as it is described in Table 2 ²³.

Table 2. Description of IC codes according to ICD-11 ²³.

Code	Description
SA90 Stony stranguria disorder (TM1)	A disorder characterized by the presence of urinary calculi, leading to painful and difficult urination due to the passage of stones. It may cause abdominal or lower back pain, and in some cases, colicky pain radiating to the perineum, or even progress to uremia. From a Traditional Chinese Medicine perspective, this condition may be attributed to the accumulation of damp-heat in the lower energizer, which steams and transforms turbid urine into retained stones in the kidneys ¹⁸ .
SA58 Abdominal pain disorder (TM1)	A disorder characterized by abdominal discomfort. It may be explained by external environmental influences, parasitic infection, improper diet, formation of calculi, <i>Qi</i> and blood deficiency or stasis, or bowel obstruction due to faecal stasis ¹⁸ .
SB07 Lower abdominal colic disorder (TM1)	A disorder characterized by intense, paroxysmal pain in the lower abdomen, constipation, or urinary retention. It may be explained by dysfunction of liver <i>Qi</i> , deficiency of <i>Qi</i> (particularly in infants or the elderly), herniation of the intestines into the scrotum due to increased abdominal pressure, traumatic injury, or blood stasis in the scrotum after surgery, or congenital malformation ¹⁸ .

3. Treatment based on TCM

3.1. Acupuncture

Acupuncture is a TCM technique which uses needles to stimulate acupoints in order to achieve homeostasis and regulate *Qi* along the meridians ¹⁷.

Acupuncture technique allows the removal of blockage or interruption of *Qi* that occurs in the meridians¹⁴. This results in the relief of symptoms and pain since the insertion of the needles in these acupoints increases the synthesis of serotonin, β -Endorphin, and enkephalin (endogenous opioids) which leads to a sensation of analgesia and sedation^{14,24}.

Acupuncture can be used to treat IC, particularly given its lack of adverse effects²⁵. There is evidence that supports a positive effect of this practice, mainly on pain relief and urinary symptoms making it a valuable option for patients with various urovaginal conditions^{25,26}.

This evidence highlights an opportunity for urologists to collaborate with other healthcare professionals, including acupuncturists²⁶.

A study enrolled 12 volunteers (female) on 10 acupuncture sessions of 25 minutes each, twice a week of the following points: SP6 (*Sanyinjiao*), SP9 (*Yinlingquan*), ST36 (*Zusanli*), LIV3 (*Tai Chong*), LI4 (*Hegu*), KID3 (*Taixi*), BL33 (*Zhongliao*) and CV4 (*Guan Yuan*)¹⁴. In the first months after treatment the procedure demonstrated 100% efficacy but, after twelve months, this rate decreased to approximately 16%¹⁴. The authors suggest that ongoing treatment may yield more consistent results¹⁴.

Another study demonstrated that electroacupuncture produces more favourable outcomes than minimal acupuncture, although both have positive results²⁷. The authors applied a protocol once a week for six weeks that includes ST30 (*Qichong*), CV2 (*Qugu*), CV4 (*Guan Yuan*), P6 (*Neiguan*), LI4 (*Hegu*), KID3 (*Taixi*), ST36 (*Zusanli*), SP4 (*Gongsun*) and found that this protocol improved pelvic floor muscles and improved pain-related quality of life²⁷.

Several other studies have demonstrated the efficacy of acupuncture in IC, some have reported that it is possible to reduce pain by using only acupoints on the Kidney and Bladder meridians. However, 10 to 20 sessions are required to obtain long-term benefits²⁸.

3.2. Diet

According to TCM, illness is a *Qi* disharmony. Therefore, to balance it and end the disease, the first and most important measure is an appropriate diet²². Each country has its own dietary and nutritional patterns. However, it is possible to find similarities between regions²⁹.

TCM nutrition has three practical applications, namely: health preservation with food, diet therapy, and longevity promotion^{29,30}. Health preservation with food is suitable for the daily diet and health care for the general population to prevent disease²⁹. Diet therapy is also known as food treatment, that is, a dietary treatment used once the disease has developed³¹.

The body extracts and absorbs *Gu Qi* (*Qi* derived from the food), so food acts almost like a therapeutic agent according to the properties of the food itself²².

In TCM there are criteria by which food is classified, such as thermal nature, flavour, organ network, and direction of energy flows³¹.

According to Traditional Chinese Medicine, in cases of IC, foods with a neutral and warm thermal nature should be preferred²². Warm foods build up the *Yang* and *Qi* and have the function of warming up the whole body and strengthening the middle burner making them suitable for treating cold symptoms and neutral foods stabilize and harmonize the body and are used to treat *Qi* vacuity²².

Bitter and sweet flavours are preferred for removing dampness, supplementing the lower burner and Kidney *Yang*, and nourishing the spleen²².

Sweet flavours increase the energy, build up Spleen *Qi* and nourish body fluids²². It also regulates inner tension, stabilizing the inner centre and helping with emotional stress²². Bitter flavour corresponds to the Fire phase and supports the body's excretion function²². It also has a calming effect when there is stress and mental strain²².

As preparation methods, boiling and frying should be preferred ²². Both methods enhance the *Yang* nature of food, which in TCM helps restore *Qi* or *Yin* vacuity ²².

3.3. Chinese Phytopharmacology

Phytotherapy is a form of treatment in which medicinal herbs are used ³². In China, phytotherapy has always been the cornerstone of Traditional Chinese Medicine, therefore phytotherapy represents 70% of the TCM practice ³².

Perhaps that is why in 2007 almost 20% of adults who used complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) also used phytotherapy ³³, which represents a cost of \$14.8 billion in the USA, \$120 per purchase ³⁴.

Herbal medicines, also called herbal agents, are used to treat many urological diseases, including recurrent cystitis and their effectiveness has already been confirmed ^{35,36}.

On the other hand, some authors argue that the efficacy remains controversial since the results rate varies between individuals ¹¹.

According to the previous TCM diagnosis the *Bei Xie Fen Qing Yin* Formula (Table 3), also known as Tokoro Formula, could be used to treat genitourinary disorders such as cystitis and dysuria since it warms up Kidney *Yang*, removes dampness, and inhibits infection ³².

Table 3. Components and herb dosage of *Bei Xie Fen Qing Yin* Formula.

Scientific Name	Amount (mg)
<i>Rhizoma Dioscoreae Tokoro</i>	78,75
<i>Fructus Alpinae Oxyphyllae</i>	78,75
<i>Rhizoma Acori Graminei</i>	78,75
<i>Radix Lindarae</i>	78,75
<i>Radix Glycyrrhizae</i>	35,00

Rhizoma Dioscoreae Tokoro eliminates dysuria, dissolves dampness, and inhibits urinary infection; *Fructus Alpinae Oxyphyllae* warms up the Kidney and Spleen and stores the *Jing* (Vital essence); *Rhizoma Acori Graminei* dissolves mucus and dampness; *Radix Lindarae* promotes *Qi* flux and disperses cold. Also inhibits pollakiuria; *Radix Glycyrrhizae* tonifies heart *Qi* and nourishes the Spleen ³².

Another highly recommended formula for treating cystitis is *Ba Zheng Tang*, also known as the *powder of the 8 corrections* (Table 4) ³⁷.

Table 4. Components and herb dosage of *Ba Zheng Tang*.

Scientific Name	Amount (g)
<i>Polygoni Avicularis Herba</i>	6
<i>Semen Plantaginis</i>	9
<i>Caulis Akebiae</i>	6
<i>Rhizoma Rhei</i>	9
<i>Fructus Gardeniae Jasminoidis</i>	6
<i>Radix Glycyrrhizae Uralensis Praeparata</i>	6

The first four components drain the damp-heat from the bladder and open the water pathway; *Rhizoma Rhei* clears the heat; *Fructus Gardeniae jasminoidis* drains damp-heat from tree heaters; *Radix Glycyrrhizae Uralensis Praeparata* harmonizes and ceases pain ³⁷.

Ginseng is well known for its rich composition, including a variety of polysaccharides, proteins, and saponins, as well as its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-cancer, anti-ageing, and immune regulation properties ³⁸. According to a study, there are 134 gin-

seng-based formulas used for IC disease³⁸. Recent studies suggest that are the anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties may help improve symptoms³⁸. However, the specific effects vary depending on the formulation, as each preparation has different targets, active components and synergetic interactions that contribute to the treatment of IC. In summary, ginseng can help reduce inflammation and tissue damage associated with IC³⁸.

A study that contemplated a total of 122 eligible patients, with 61 cases in each group (antibiotic group and Chinese Medicine (CM) group). The clinical cure rate by the intention-to-treat approach was 90.2% for the Chinese Medicine group and 82.0% for the antibiotic group ($P>0.05$)². Bacteria were eliminated from 88.5% (54/61) of patients in the CM group and 82.0% (50/61) in the antibiotic group. The recurrence rate in recovered patients at 6-month follow-up was 9.1% (5/61) and 14.0 (7/61) in the CM and antibiotic groups, respectively ($P>0.05$)². The CM formula was derived from an ancient remedy Ba Zheng Powder (Table 5), that was officially recorded in the *Song* Dynasty and comprised 10 herbs. This formula has been proven to be effective by both clinical practice and experimental studies^{39,40}.

Table 5. Components and herb dosage of Bazheng Powder Formula.

Scientific Name	Amount (g)
<i>Anemarrhena asphodeloides</i> Bunge	15
<i>Platyclusus orientalis</i> (L.) Franco	10
<i>Angelica sinensis</i> (Oliv.) Diels	10
<i>Rehmannia glutinosa</i> (Gaertn.) DC	15
<i>Poria cocos</i> (Schw.) Wolf	15
<i>Salvia miltiorrhiza</i> Bunge	10
<i>Rheum palmatum</i> L.	6
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i> L.	10
<i>Dianthus superbus</i> L.	10
Talcum	15

Another study used a decoction composed of *Cornus*, *Gardenia*, *Curculigo*, *Rhubarb*, *Psoralea* and *Rehmannia*, *Discoria*, *Poria*, *Morinda*, *Coscuta* and *Anemarrhea* twice a day, six days a week, for three months and then once a week⁴¹. After four weeks of treatment, 61% of the 25 patients reported a significant decrease in pain⁴¹.

3.4. Qigong and Tai Chi

Qigong is an oriental practice that involves body and mind exercises (movement, respiration and meditation) whose objective is to achieve physical and psychological well-being⁴².

Tai Chi, also known as Taiji, Taijiquan or Tai chi chuan, like *Qigong* is a low-intensity mind-body exercise that improves aerobic capacity, strength, balance and psychological well-being⁴³.

Tai Chi and *Qigong* can be framed as an energy therapy useful for maintaining health. As it was proven in a systematic review, Tai Chi and *Qigong* can improve physical function, the immunity system and quality of life⁴⁴. Although there isn't enough scientific evidence about the influence of *Qigong* in IC, its effectiveness in managing chronic pain is well established. In fact, magnetic resonance imaging has shown that *Qigong* training can activate brain regions responsible for pain suppression^{45,46}. However, efficiency varies from individual to individual according to his confidence, training and regularity¹¹.

Although there are no specific exercises to treat IC, some can be recommended for chronic inflammation of the urogenital system, namely the smoothing method of Five Elements Palm. These exercises nourish blood and calm the spirit⁴⁷.

The starting posture (Figure 1) consists of standing naturally with feet shoulder-width apart, parallel, standing with knees slightly bent, and the arms hanging down. Bend the wrists so the palms face upward, with fingertips pointing toward each other, and position the hands in front of the *Dantian* as if holding an object ⁴⁷.

While inhaling, guide the clear *Qi* upwards along the Heart channel. While exhaling, silently pronounce “HE”, focusing the mind on expelling turbid *Qi* ⁴⁷.

At the same time, raise both hands as if holding an object at chest level, with legs in a horse stance (Figure 2) Then move the extended arms horizontally from left to right, in palmar flexion (Figure 3), allowing the body to move slowly to the right. At the end of the movement, turn the palms upward ⁴⁷.

Then, exhale and turn the palms inwards and downwards while bending the arms and squatting, keeping the upper body straight and returning to the horse stance ⁴⁷. After repeating the process 3-9 times on the right side, switch to the right leg and perform the movements from the right to the left 3-9 times ⁴⁷.

Roborant *Qigong* can also be applied to urogenital pathologies. This form of training is recognized for its ability to nourish *Qi* and strengthen Kidney energy. To achieve its therapeutic effects, it must be practised for 20 minutes, 2-3 times a day for at least three months ⁴⁷.

Figure 1. Inicial Posture ⁶⁴.

Figure 2. Horse Position ⁶⁴.

Figure 3. Palm flexion ⁶⁴.

The practice method allows flexibility in choosing the postures which may include natural cross-legs, half-lotus, full-lotus, standing or free posture. Once the posture is selected, the practitioner can choose one of three types of breathing:

- Quiet breathing – breathing naturally without focusing attention on it;
- Deep breathing - while inhaling, both the chest and the abdomen expand ⁴⁷. While exhaling, both retract ⁴⁷.
- Reverse abdominal breathing- while inhaling, the chest expands and the abdomen retracts; while exhaling, the chest retracts and the abdomen distends ⁴⁷.

Following this, the practitioner proceeds to mind adjustment and choosing between two techniques: guided imagination or keeping the ‘mind on’ ⁴⁷.

In the first one, the practitioner should guide the imagination according to his condition or illness and use the suggestive power of imagination to create the ideal environment of the body, like hot, warm, cold, etc ⁴⁷. IC patients may imagine a fireball in the abdomen.

Keeping the 'mind on' consists of focusing on body areas according to the physical condition such as the *dantian*, kidneys or even acupoints⁴⁷.

4. Treatment based on Naturopathy

Naturopathy may represent an underutilized resource in advancing the understanding and management of urinary tract pathologies⁴⁸. The therapeutic focus in interstitial cystitis is directed toward restoring the integrity of the bladder interstitium and reinforcing the urothelial lining²⁶. Counselling should include guidance on identifying and avoiding personal symptom triggers²⁶. Stress reduction strategies and engagement with support groups are also encouraged to help patients cope with the condition's impact on daily life²⁶. Additionally, dietary modifications have been shown to contribute to symptomatic relief in many cases, as botanical medicines and other complementary treatments²⁶.

Patient education plays a crucial role in the management of interstitial cystitis, empowering individuals to actively participate in their treatment and symptom control²⁶.

4.1. Biofeedback

Biofeedback enhances voluntary control over typically involuntary physiological functions by converting internal biological signals into external sensory cues, such as visual or auditory feedback. Through training and positive reinforcement, individuals can learn to modulate these signals and develop greater control over specific bodily functions⁴⁹.

In the context of pelvic health, biofeedback therapy allows patients to visualize the activity of their pelvic floor muscles via a computer interface. This visual input facilitates awareness and conscious control over muscular contractions, effectively disrupting the spasm-pain cycle commonly observed in interstitial cystitis⁴¹.

A study involving 48 patients diagnosed with IC implemented a 12-week pelvic floor muscle training program combined with biofeedback. The intervention focused on enhancing muscle relaxation and coordination, resulting in symptom improvement in 80% of participants and enhanced quality of life in 70%. Significant reductions in urinary frequency and pain levels were also reported⁵⁰.

Moreover, sessions lasting 30 to 60 minutes weekly over six weeks have demonstrated notable efficacy in reducing pain and alleviating muscle tenderness²⁶.

4.2. L-arginine

L-arginine is a key substrate in the biosynthesis of nitric oxide (NO), a process catalyzed by nitric oxide synthases (NOS). NO acts as a versatile signalling molecule with distinct roles in various physiological systems. In the central nervous system, it functions as a neurotransmitter; within the immune system, it supports host defence mechanisms; and in the cardiovascular system, it contributes to vascular homeostasis by promoting vasodilation and exerting anti-atherogenic effects on the endothelium⁵¹.

A study observed that patients with IC exhibited decreased nitric oxide synthase (NOS) production compared to healthy controls. In a randomized, double-blind trial, 10 patients with IC were administered oral L-arginine at a dose of 1.5 grams per day for six months. The results indicated an increase in urinary NOS levels and an improvement in clinical symptoms including urinary frequency and nocturia in 8 out of the 10 patients⁵².

However, evidence on the efficacy of L-arginine remains mixed. A randomized, double-blind, controlled trial found no clinically significant improvement in IC symptoms with L-arginine supplementation⁵⁰. Conversely, another randomized, double-blind, controlled study reported a significant improvement in IC symptoms in the per-protocol analysis, though the intent-to-treat analysis showed no significant difference between the L-arginine and placebo groups⁵¹.

4.3. Probiotics

Probiotics are live microorganisms that, when administered in adequate amounts, confer health benefits to the host⁵³.

A patient survey investigating probiotic use among individuals with IC revealed that 58.8% of 442 respondents reported significant symptom relief, based on self-assessment⁵⁴.

4.4. *Arctostaphylos uva ursi*

Although traditional use of *Arctostaphylos uva ursi* for symptomatic relief of mild recurrent lower urinary tract infections such as burning sensation during urination and/or frequent urination in women⁵⁵, there is currently no clinical evidence supporting its efficacy in IC.

4.5. Cranberry (*Vaccinium macrocarpon*) juice

The urothelium of the bladder is safeguarded by a dense glycosaminoglycan (GAG) layer, which serves as a critical component of the bladder's barrier function. This protective layer offers both physical and electrostatic defence against urinary irritants, pathogens, and acidic substances, thereby preventing their penetration into the underlying bladder wall⁵⁶.

Although cranberry is recognized for its rich content of polyphenols, including flavonoids and phenolic acids, which have shown beneficial effects in the prevention of urinary tract infections (UTIs)⁵⁷, its use is not recommended for individuals with interstitial cystitis (IC). This caution stems from cranberry juice's low pH (approximately 2.5) and its high concentrations of organic acids such as citric, malic, and quinic acids⁵⁷. These compounds contribute to the juice's high titratable acidity, which may irritate the bladder mucosa and consequently worsen IC symptoms⁵⁸.

4.6. Diet

Several studies have demonstrated that specific foods and beverages may exacerbate the symptoms of interstitial cystitis. Dietary triggers often include acidic, spicy, caffeinated, or carbonated items, which can irritate the bladder mucosa and contribute to symptom flare-ups. Given this strong correlation, the American Urological Association (AUA) recommends dietary modification as a first-line intervention in the management of IC¹.

The "Events Preceding Interstitial Cystitis" case-control study revealed that 85% of individuals with IC reported symptom flare-ups following the consumption of specific foods or beverages⁵⁹. This finding was corroborated by a secondary analysis of the Interstitial Cystitis Database cohort, which found that 77% of patients demonstrated some degree of food sensitivity⁵⁹. Furthermore, a survey involving 598 IC patients showed that 95.8% observed a direct link between dietary intake and symptom exacerbation⁶⁰.

A growing body of evidence has established a clear association between particular dietary components and symptom modulation in IC, with certain items intensifying discomfort while others appear to provide relief⁴. Acidic foods and beverages, especially those rich in citric acid, as well as foods high in arylalkylamines, have been implicated in symptom aggravation²¹.

Some studies suggest that elevated urinary potassium enhances bladder urothelial permeability, leading to increased pain due to the leaky epithelium⁶¹. Dietary potassium restriction is often recommended, but evidence remains inconclusive due to limited studies and inconsistent patient responses⁴.

Regarding the timing of symptom onset, a study using three-day food and voiding diaries found that symptoms typically flare within two to four hours after consuming potential irritants⁴¹. However, more recent findings indicate considerable individual variability, with some patients experiencing symptoms within minutes, while others report delayed responses of up to 24 hours⁶².

Despite ongoing uncertainty about the exact pathophysiological mechanisms involved, dietary modification is widely regarded as a first-line therapeutic strategy for IC, as endorsed by the American Urological Association¹. Given the variability in individual food sensitivities, personalized dietary plans are essential. The standard approach involves an initial elimination of suspected irritants for a period of 2–3 months, followed by a gradual reintroduction to identify specific triggers⁴¹. Alternatively, some clinicians recommend that patients maintain their usual diet while tracking symptoms, subsequently focusing on the least provocative foods for a two-week period. If symptoms remain stable, additional foods can be reintroduced at three-day intervals to construct a long-term dietary plan⁴.

Table 6. Foods and Beverages: Most and Least Symptom-Inducing⁶³.

	Most Bothersome	Least Bothersome
Vegetables		Avocados
		Asparagus
		Beets
		Broccoli
		Brussels Sprouts
		Cabbage
		Carrots
		Cauliflower
		Celery
		Cucumber
		Eggplant
		Mushrooms
		Peas
	Potatoes (white potatoes, yams, sweet potatoes)	
	Radishes	
	Spinach	
	Squash	
	Turnips	
	Zucchini	
Fruits		Apricots
		Bananas
		Blueberries
		Dates
		Melon (honeydew and watermelon)
		Prunes
		Pears
	Raisins	
Dairy	Yoghurt	Milk (low-fat and whole)
		Cheeses (mild)
Protein Foods		Beef
	Processed sandwich meats (salami, Bologna)	Fish (shrimp, tuna fish and salmon)
	Soy	Eggs
		Nuts
		Peanut butter
	Pork	

		Poultry (chicken and turkey)
		Lamb
Grains		Oats Rice
	Chili Horseradish Ketchup Salad Dressings Soy sauce Vinegar Worcester Sauce	Herbs Garlic or any herb-infused olive oil
Condiments		
	Alcohol Coffee (caffeinated and decaffeinated) Tea (caffeinated and decaffeinated) Carbonated drinks (cola, non-cola, diet, and caffeine-free) Cranberry juice	Grain beverages/Coffee substitutes Water
Beverages		
	Chocolate Indian food Mexican food Pizza Spicy foods Thai food	Popcorn Pretzels
Other Foods		
Additives/Artificial Sweeteners	Artificial sweeteners Monosodium glutamate (MSG)	

4.7. General Measures

Patients should be advised to maintain adequate fluid intake, consuming at least 2 litres per day²⁶.

Additionally, patients should be instructed to urinate after intercourse. Women who experience bladder infections following intercourse may benefit from washing the labia and urethra with a strong infusion of *Hydrangea canadensis* (2 teaspoons per cup) both before and after. If this is not effective, a dilute solution of povidone-iodine is generally helpful²⁶.

5. Conclusion

Despite the high prevalence of interstitial cystitis and its substantial impact on patients' quality of life, the diagnosis of this condition remains complex, primarily relying on exclusion criteria.

This is closely linked to its multifactorial pathogenesis, the existence of multiple, sometimes conflicting, etiological theories, and significant limitations in the existing literature. Even the American Urological Association (AUA) acknowledges that its clinical guidelines were developed with an awareness of these limitations.

Among the non-pharmacological strategies recommended by the AUA, lifestyle and behavioural modifications are emphasized.

However, the specific nature of these behavioural changes is not clearly defined. Within this context, TCM and Naturopathy appear to align with these recommendations by promoting holistic changes through dietary modifications, the integration of *Qigong* into daily routines, and the use of herbal medicine and supplements.

Although the current scientific evidence is limited, preliminary studies suggest that both TCM and Naturopathy may offer valuable complementary strategies in the management of IC. These findings are consistent with the core philosophies of each approach, TCM seeks to restore the balance of *Qi* to prevent and treat disease, whereas Naturopathy supports the body's intrinsic self-healing processes.

Concerning TCM, there is a notably greater investment in scientific evidence related to acupuncture, whereas the other areas receive considerably less attention. Consequently, for these remaining areas, most of the available information is derived from classical texts rather than recent scientific literature. In our research, we were unable to find studies on the effectiveness of these techniques, which highlights a significant gap in the evidence.

This review has made it possible to propose a preliminary framework for the integration of these practices into the management of IC. Notably, they are not mutually exclusive and may be used in conjunction with other approaches, promoting a more comprehensive and individualized treatment plan.

Given their low incidence of adverse effects and potential benefits, further high-quality, long-term studies are urgently needed to validate the efficacy of these interventions. Future research should also assess their cost-effectiveness compared to conventional treatments, especially considering the economic burden associated with IC.

Credit author statement: Conceptualization: C.L.; Investigation: C.L.; M.G.S.; R.P.S.; Project Administration: C.L.; Supervision: C.L.; Writing – Original Draft Preparation: C.L.; M.G.S.; R.P.S.; Writing – Review & Editing: C.L.; M.G.S.; R.P.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

References

1. Hanno PM, Burks DA, Clemens JQ, Dmochowski RR, Erickson D, FitzGerald MP, et al. AUA Guideline for the Diagnosis and Treatment of Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome. *Journal of Urology*. 2011 Mar;185:2162–70.
2. Liu S wei, Guo J, Wu W kang, Chen Z liang, Zhang N. Treatment of Uncomplicated Recurrent Urinary Tract Infection with Chinese Medicine Formula: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Chin J Integr Med*. 2017 Mar;25:16–22.
3. Hanno P, Dmochowski R. Status of international consensus on interstitial cystitis/bladder pain syndrome/painful bladder syndrome: 2008 snapshot. *Neurourol Urodyn*. 2009 May;28:274–86.
4. Friedlander JI, Shorter B, Moldwin RM. Diet and its role in interstitial cystitis/bladder pain syndrome (IC/BPS) and comorbid conditions. *BJU Int*. 2012 Mar;109:1584–91.
5. Chiu K, Zhang F, Sutcliffe S, Mysorekar IU, Lowder JL. Recurrent Urinary Tract Infection Incidence Rates Decrease in Women With Cystitis Cystica After Treatment With d-Mannose: A Cohort Study. *Female Pelvic Med Reconstr Surg*. 2022 May;28:e62–5.
6. Clemens JQ, Meenan RT, O'Keeffe Rosetti MC, Kimes T, Calhoun EA. Costs of Interstitial Cystitis in a Managed Care Population. *Urology*. 2008 May;71:776–80.

7. Payne CK, Joyce GF, Wise M, Clemens JQ. Interstitial Cystitis and Painful Bladder Syndrome. *Journal of Urology*. 2007 May;177:2042–9.
8. Clemens JQ, Markossian T, Calhoun EA. Comparison of Economic Impact of Chronic Prostatitis/Chronic Pelvic Pain Syndrome and Interstitial Cystitis/Painful Bladder Syndrome. *Urology*. 2009 May;73:743–6.
9. Jhang JF, Jiang YH, Kuo HC. Current Understanding of the Pathophysiology and Novel Treatments of Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome. *Biomedicines*. 2022 May;10:2380.
10. Lim Y, Leslie SW, O'Rourke S. Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome [Internet]. StatPearls Publishing; 2024. Available from: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK570588/#_article-132252_s3
11. Pang R, Ali A. The Chinese approach to complementary and alternative medicine treatment for interstitial cystitis/bladder pain syndrome. *Transl Androl Urol* [Internet]. 2015 Mar;4:653–61. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4708546/>
12. Fleming SA, Gutknecht NC. Naturopathy and the Primary Care Practice. *Primary Care: Clinics in Office Practice* [Internet]. 2010 Jan;37:119–36. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2883816/>
13. Liu Y, Zhang P, Liu M, Liu X, Liu R, Yu X, et al. The clinical effect of traditional chinese medicine on middle-aged women with Interstitial Cystitis. *Medicine* [Internet]. 2020 Mar;99:e19673. Available from: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7440324/>
14. Sönmez MG, Kozaňhan B. Complete response to acupuncture therapy in female patients with refractory interstitial cystitis/bladder pain syndrome. *Ginekol Pol*. 2017 Mar;88:61–7.
15. Chung KJ, Han ANY, Kim KH. Recommendations to the primary care practitioners and the patients for managing pelvic pain, especially in painful bladder syndrome for early and better prognosis. *J Exerc Rehabil* [Internet]. 2015 May;11:251–4. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26535214/>
16. Konkle KS, Berry SH, Elliott MN, Hilton L, Suttorp MJ, Clauw DJ, et al. Comparison of an Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome Clinical Cohort With Symptomatic Community Women From the RAND Interstitial Cystitis Epidemiology Study. *Journal of Urology*. 2012 May;187:508–12.
17. Leong FC. Complementary and Alternative Medications for Chronic Pelvic Pain. *Obstet Gynecol Clin North Am*. 2014 Mar;41:503–10.
18. van Ginkel C, Hurst RE, Janssen D. The urothelial barrier in interstitial cystitis/bladder pain syndrome: its form and function, an overview of preclinical models. *Curr Opin Urol* [Internet]. 2024 May;34:77–83. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10842656/>
19. Bicer F, Altuntas CZ, Izgi K, Ozer A, Kavran M, Tuohy VK, et al. Chronic pelvic allodynia is mediated by CCL2 through mast cells in an experimental autoimmune cystitis model. *AJP Renal Physiology*. 2014 May;308:F103–13.
20. Grundy L, Caldwell A, Brierley SM. Mechanisms Underlying Overactive Bladder and Interstitial Cystitis/Painful Bladder Syndrome. *Front Neurosci* [Internet]. 2018;12:931. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30618560>
21. Abercrombie PD, Learman LA. Providing Holistic Care for Women with Chronic Pelvic Pain. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*. 2012 Mar;41:668–79.
22. Kastner J. Chinese Nutrition Therapy [Internet]. 2025. Available from: https://books.google.pt/books/about/Chinese_Nutrition_Therapy.html?id=80CqL7u0KdIC&redir_esc=y
23. Organisation WH. ICD-11 for Mortality and Morbidity Statistics [Internet]. 2024. Available from: <https://icd.who.int/browse/2024-01/mms/en>
24. Cabýoglu Mt, Ergene N, Tan U. The Mechanism of Acupuncture and Clinical Applications. *International Journal of Neuroscience*. 2006 Mar;116:115–25.

25. Lee SH, Lee BC. Use of Acupuncture as a Treatment Method for Chronic Prostatitis/Chronic Pelvic Pain Syndromes. *Curr Urol Rep*. 2011 Mar;12:288–96.
26. Pizzorno J, Murray MT. *Textbook of natural medicine*. St. Louis, Mo. Elsevier; 2013.
27. Bresler L, Westbay LC, Hekman L, Joyce C, Fitzgerald CM. Acupuncture for female bladder pain syndrome: a randomized controlled trial. *Can J Urol [Internet]*. 2022 Mar;29:11154–61. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35691037/>
28. Taylor J. Acupuncture Therapy for Interstitial Cystitis (Bladder Pain Syndrome): A Case Report. *Convergent Points: An East-West Case Report Journal [Internet]*. 2023;2. Available from: <https://www.convergentpoints.com/article/view/19>
29. Xinyu Zhao Xinggui THSDX. Nutrition and traditional Chinese medicine (TCM): a system's theoretical perspective [Internet]. 2020. Available from: <https://ouci.dntb.gov.ua/en/works/4wxV3kYI/>
30. Wu Q, Liang X. Food therapy and medical diet therapy of Traditional Chinese Medicine. *Clin Nutr Exp*. 2018 Mar;18:1–5.
31. Wu Q, Liang X. Food therapy and medical diet therapy of Traditional Chinese Medicine. *Clin Nutr Exp*. 2018 Mar;18:1–5.
32. Cheng L Der. *Fórmulas Magistrais Chinasas*. Editora Roca; 2008.
33. Barnes PM, Bloom B, Nahin RL. Complementary and alternative medicine use among adults and children: United States, 2007. *Natl Health Stat Report [Internet]*. 2008 Mar;12:1–23. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19361005/>
34. Nahin RL, Barnes PM, Stussman BJ, Bloom B. Costs of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) and frequency of visits to CAM practitioners: United States, 2007. *Natl Health Stat Report [Internet]*. 2009 Mar;1–14. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19771719/>
35. Kranz J, Lackner J, Künzel U, Wagenlehner F, Schmidt S. Phytotherapy in adults with recurrent uncomplicated cystitis. *Dtsch Arztebl Int*. 2022 Mar;
36. Morán E, Budía A, Broseta E, Boronat F. Fitoterapia en Urología. Evidencia científica actual de su aplicación en urolitiasis, dolor pélvico crónico, disfunción eréctil e infecciones urinarias. *Actas Urol Esp*. 2013 Mar;37:174–80.
37. Maciocia G. *A prática da medicina chinesa : tratamento das doenças com acupuntura e ervas chinesas*. Roca; 2010.
38. Wang L, Yuan L. Analysis of ginseng in the treatment of Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome based on network pharmacology. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci [Internet]*. 2022 Mar;26:4709–20. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35856363/>
39. Zhang N, Huang L, Liu S, Wang Y, Luo Y, Jin X, et al. Traditional chinese medicine: an alternative treatment option for refractory recurrent urinary tract infections. *Clin Infect Dis [Internet]*. 2013 Mar;56:1355. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23362289/>
40. Liu SW, Xu XY, Xu J, Yuan JY, Wu WK, Zhang N, et al. Multi-drug resistant uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* and its treatment by Chinese medicine. *Chin J Integr Med [Internet]*. 2017 Mar;23:763–9. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28028717/>
41. Whitmore KE. Complementary and alternative therapies as treatment approaches for interstitial cystitis. *Rev Urol [Internet]*. 2002;4 Suppl 1:S28–35. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16986031/>
42. Antonelli M, Donelli D. Evaluating qigong as integrative support for COVID-19 and Long-COVID-19 rehabilitation: a systematic review. *Front Psychol*. 2024 Jul;15.
43. Qi F, Soh KG, Mohd J, Mai Y. Effects of taichi on physical and psychological health of college students: A systematic review. *Front Physiol*. 2022 Mar;13.
44. Jahnke R, Larkey L, Rogers C, Etnier J, Lin F. A Comprehensive Review of Health Benefits of Qigong and Tai Chi. *American Journal of Health Promotion [Internet]*. 2010 Mar;24:e1–25. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3085832/>
45. Lee MS, Pittler MH, Ernst E. External Qigong for Pain Conditions: A Systematic Review of Randomized Clinical Trials. *J Pain*. 2007 Mar;8:827–31.

46. Yu WL, Li XQ, Tang WJ, Li Y, Weng XC, Chen YZ. fMRI Study of Pain Reaction in the Brain under State of “Qigong.” *Am J Chin Med* (Gard City N Y). 2007 Mar;35:937–45.
47. Liu T. Chinese medical qigong. Singing Dragon; 2013.
48. Garofalo L, Zwickey H, Bradley R, Hanes D. Naturopathic Management of Urinary Tract Infections: A Retrospective Chart Review. *The Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*. 2021 Mar;
49. Malik K, Dua A. Biofeedback [Internet]. StatPearls Publishing; 2021. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK553075/>
50. Borrego-Jimenez PS, Flores-Fraile J, Padilla-Fernández BY, Valverde-Martinez S, Gómez-Prieto A, Márquez-Sánchez MT, et al. Improvement in Quality of Life with Pelvic Floor Muscle Training and Biofeedback in Patients with Painful Bladder Syndrome/Interstitial Cystitis. *J Clin Med*. 2021 Mar;10:862.
51. Böger RH. The Pharmacodynamics of L-Arginine. *J Nutr*. 2007 Apr;137:1650S-1655S.
52. Cartledge JJ, Davies AM, Eardley I. A randomized double-blind placebo-controlled crossover trial of the efficacy of l-arginine in the treatment of interstitial cystitis. *BJU Int*. 2000 Mar;85:421–6.
53. Hill C, Guarner F, Reid G, Gibson GR, Merenstein DJ, Pot B, et al. The International Scientific Association for Probiotics and Prebiotics consensus statement on the scope and appropriate use of the term probiotic. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2014;11:506–14.
54. O'Hare PG, Hoffmann AR, Allen P, Gordon B, Salin L, Whitmore K. Interstitial cystitis patients' use and rating of complementary and alternative medicine therapies. *Int Urogynecol J*. 2012 Mar;24:977–82.
55. Assessment report on *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* (L.) Spreng., folium. London: EMA. Doc. Ref.: EMA/HMPC/573462/2009 Rev.1. Adopted: 24 January 2012. [Internet]. 2024. Available from: <https://www.fitoterapia.net/publicaciones/documentacion/assessment-report-arctostaphylos-ursi-spreng.-1793.html>
56. McLennan MT. Interstitial Cystitis. *Obstet Gynecol Clin North Am*. 2014 Mar;41:385–95.
57. González-Rico P, Guerrero-Barona E, Chambel MJ, Guerrero-Molina M. Well-Being at Work: Burnout and Engagement Profiles of University Workers. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* [Internet]. 2022 Jul;19:15436. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/19/23/15436>
58. Renaud V, Faucher M, Perreault V, Serre E, Dubé P, Boutin Y, et al. Evolution of cranberry juice compounds during in vitro digestion and identification of the organic acid responsible for the disruption of in vitro intestinal cell barrier integrity. *J Food Sci Technol*. 2020 Mar;57:2329–42.
59. Warren JW, Brown J, Tracy JK, Langenberg P, Wesselmann U, Greenberg P. Evidence-Based Criteria for Pain of Interstitial Cystitis/Painful Bladder Syndrome in Women. *Urology*. 2008 Mar;71:444–8.
60. Bassaly R, Downes K, Hart S. Dietary Consumption Triggers in Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome Patients. *Female Pelvic Med Reconstr Surg*. 2011 Mar;17:36–9.
61. Parsons CL. The role of a leaky epithelium and potassium in the generation of bladder symptoms in interstitial cystitis/overactive bladder, urethral syndrome, prostatitis and gynaecological chronic pelvic pain. *BJU Int*. 2010 May;107:370–5.
62. Shorter B, Ackerman M, Varvara M, Moldwin RM. Statistical Validation of the Shorter-Moldwin Food Sensitivity Questionnaire for Patients with Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome. *J Urol*. 2014 Mar;191:1793–801.
63. Association IC. Least and Most Bothersome Foods | Interstitial Cystitis Association [Internet]. 2022. Available from: <https://www.ichelp.org/least-and-most-bothersome-foods/>
64. zhzyw [Internet]. 2017. Available from: <https://www.zhzyw.com/zyts/zyqg/gf/174261015AAJ35DD46H4FGCJ.html>